

Performance management in medium-sized enterprises

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Abstract

The purpose of the study is to investigate ways in which performance management is practiced in medium-sized enterprises in Sri Lanka. Medium-sized enterprises in Sri Lanka with the total number of employees between 50 to 99, more than 7 years of business operation, and total investment between 5 to 50 million Sri Lankan Rupees were surveyed. The hypothesized relationships were examined by structural equation modelling. It was found that the six characteristics of performance management, namely, focus, target setting, administrative work procedures, interdependency, integration with other HRM functions and responsibility significantly predict performance management effectiveness. Although medium-sized enterprises in the sample have devoted considerable energy in implementing performance management practices, considerable improvements are needed in the level of adoption.

Key words medium-sized enterprises, performance management, SME

Introduction

Small and medium enterprises (SMEs) play a pivotal role in the socio-economic development of any country, worldwide, due to their share in employment and gross domestic product (Ardic, Mylenko, & Saltane, 2011; Kushnir, Mirmulstein, & Ramalho, 2010). Yet, scholars (such as Ates & Bititci, 2011) argued that the needs and challenges of SMEs to survive in the business world are not well researched. Although SMEs face resource constraints of time, money and human capital, SMEs have a desire to pursue long-term strategic changes to be resilient and sustainable in the contemporary business world (Moore & Manring, 2009). In this regard, Wijetunge (2014), Kiriri (2005) and Stonehouse and Pemberton

(2002) provided evidence for SMEs' trend to adopt a long term view by undertaking some form of business planning in Sri Lanka, Australia, and the UK, respectively. Further, SMEs are in the process of reaping the benefits of information technology to enhance their supply chain efficiency by adopting technologies such as electronic data interchange and e-commerce (Gunasekaran, Rai, & Griffin, 2011). Furthermore, Panizzolo, Garengo, Sharma and Gore (2012) provided evidence that Indian SMEs have realized the importance of adopting lean manufacturing systems. Therefore, scholars (such as Gunasekaran et al., 2011; Salavou, Baltas, & Lioukas, 2004) argued that SMEs can be innovative and flexible in adapting to change due to their size advantage over large enterprises. However, previous studies of Zheng, O'Neill and Morrison (2009), Cunningham and Rowley (2007) and Hornsby and Kuratko (2003) reported that the size of SMEs influences their capacity to adopt appropriate management practices. Although the majority of studies available in the literature consider both small and medium size enterprises as a single category, it is evident from some previous studies such as Cunningham and Rowley (2007), Wijetunge (2014) and Zheng et al. (2009) that the size of the SME is an important factor in studying management practices. Further, Headd and Sadee (2008) state that mixing data across the enterprises of different size, particularly the number of employees, can distort research results, and emphasised the need of being specific on the size of the enterprises being investigated.

In the above context, present study investigates performance management practices of medium-sized enterprises in Sri Lanka. Previous studies had investigated performance management, considered SMEs in general - considering both small and medium size enterprises as a single category, and revealed that SMEs find difficulties in the use of performance management (e.g. Brown and Heywood, 2005; Chen, 2011; Kiriri, 2005; Soltani, van der Meer, Gennard, & Williams, 2004; Stonehouse & Pemberton, 2002; Wijetunge, 2014; Zheng et al., 2009). However, making conclusions on the practice of

performance management in medium-sized enterprises based on the results of these studies have become difficult. As a result, there is a lack of research in performance management in medium-sized enterprises; this area remains an important topic of investigation among organisational researchers and practitioners. Therefore, the essential contribution of the present study lies in presenting empirical data on performance management as it is *actually* practiced by the medium-sized enterprises in Sri Lanka.

The specific objectives of the study were to investigate 1) the nature of performance targets and performance criteria used by medium-sized enterprises in Sri Lanka, 2) characteristics of performance management, and 3) characteristics of performance management that predict performance management effectiveness in medium-sized enterprises. The present study was confined to empirically investigate performance management as it is *actually* practiced by medium-sized enterprises.

Review of literature

Performance management

The term performance management refers to a range of integrated activities continuously performed by a firm to enhance the performance of a target individual or group by setting expectations, reviewing results, and rewarding performance (DeNisi, 2011; Gravina & Siers, 2011; Molleman & Timmerman, 2003). The overall purpose of performance management is to ensure that the subsystems of organisation are aligned and complement each other in an optimal fashion to achieve results desired by the organisation (Biron, Farndale, & Paauwe, 2011). Therefore, performance management should be integrated in two senses, i.e., vertical and horizontal. Vertical integration implies the alignment of corporate, team and individual objectives while horizontal integration implies the alignment of different HRM activities to

produce a coherent approach in managing people (Biron et al., 2011; McAdam, Hazlett, & Casey, 2005).

When considering vertical integration, a firm's performance management should be based on performance targets or key performance indicators by translating organisational strategies into operational terms (de Waal, 2003; Kuvaas, 2007; Gravina&Siers, 2011). Accordingly, organisational, departmental, team and individual goals should support each other. Ultimately, individual goals that are deduced from the organisational goals should be in clear, reliable, pre-set measurable terms to make an assessment of the contribution (Abu-Doleh& Weir, 2007; Manoharan, Muralidharan, & Deshmukh, 2011; Soltani et al., 2004). Specifically, performance measurement at the individual level should reflect job-related behaviour with a greater level of specificity in the definition of outcomes and in harmony with performance standards compared to organizational performance measures (Manoharan et al., 2011; Soltani et al., 2004).

When considering the horizontal integration, performance management systems should be able to furnish valid and useful information to make the decisions of rewards administration, employee retention/termination, employee potential, and many other managerial decisions (Abu-Doleh& Weir, 2007; Biron et al., 2011; Shrivastava&Purang, 2011; Soltani et al., 2004). These uses of performance management information will provide a clear signal of what is valued by the organisation (Biron et al., 2011) and a reinforcement for desired employee outcomes (Haines III & St-Onge, 2012; Soltani et al., 2004).

The review of literature suggests it is very rare to find previous studies that specifically investigated performance management in medium-sized enterprises. However, few previous studies are available on performance management in SMEs, which consider both small and medium size enterprises as a single category (e.g. Brown and Heywood, 2005; Chen, 2011; Kiriri, 2005; Soltani et al., 2004; Stonehouse& Pemberton, 2002; Wijetunge,

2014; Zheng et al., 2009). These studies suggest that SMEs, in general, face difficulties in the practice of performance management. For instance, Chen (2011) found that SMEs find difficulties in the skillful implementation and use of performance management. Soltani et al. (2004) found that SMEs rarely use performance management information for diagnosing training and development needs. Although some previous studies provide evidence that SMEs develop business plans in accordance with enterprise goals, these studies had not provided evidence for its connection to HRM plans (e.g., Kiriri, 2005; Stonehouse & Pemberton, 2002; Wijetunge, 2014). Further, although some other studies provide evidence for the existence of performance management, they had not provided evidence for either vertical or horizontal integration (e.g., Chen, 2011; Zheng et al., 2009). In this regard, Brown and Heywood (2005) argued that any attempt to manage performance in SMEs should be in an integrated manner providing the best available avenues for employees to exert effort, assigning them to the most appropriate jobs, setting pay levels, and making decisions on their potential. Otherwise, Haines III & St-Onge (2012) state that organisations will fail to realize the full potential contribution of performance management to organisational effectiveness. However, it should be noted that these studies did not make a distinction in terms of the size of SME.

Performance management characteristics

The review of literature suggests several characteristics of effective performance management systems. Some of such characteristics are clarity, relevance, recognition, goal setting, the provision of feedback, the regular use of the system by the organisation, and the utilization of information by the organisation (Biron et al., 2011; de Waal, 2003; Kuvaas, 2007; Shrivastava & Purang, 2011). For instance, the use of performance management

information for development purposes positively influences employees' satisfaction with performance management (Boswell & Boudreau, 2000).

Further, ways in which performance management information is utilized signals employees' value to the organisation and future prospects within the organisation (Boswell & Boudreau, 2000). Furthermore, employees' beliefs in performance management in terms of evaluation criteria, the role of supervisor, trust and confidence in the supervisor, the knowledge of performance management process, and the shared sense of commitment to each other are also important characteristics of performance management that create positive reactions (Boswell & Boudreau, 2000; Gravina&Siers, 2011; Selvarajan&Cloninger, 2012; Shrivastava&Purang, 2011).

The use of goal-oriented performance management, where employees have input into the process, would also create a positive perception in employees than one without such involvement (Pettijohn, Pettijohn, &d'Amico, 2001; Shrivastava&Purang, 2011; Soltani et al., 2004). The culture of performance management, the provision of appropriate mechanisms, and top management involvement are also identified as factors that reinforce desired employee outcomes (Biron et al., 2011; Boswell & Boudreau, 2000; Brown & Heywood,2005; Cook & Crossman, 2004).

Performance management effectiveness

According to Ahmed (1999, p. 543), "an assessment of any organisational activity, in general, is a complex process because there is little agreement on the definition of 'effectiveness' and its measurement". This is due to the subjective nature of the term *effectiveness*. In the context of performance management, Haines III and St-Onge (2012) and Biron et al. (2011) had not conceptualized the meaning of performance management effectiveness in their studies on performance management effectiveness. In the present study, performance management

effectiveness is viewed as a multi-dimensional construct and confined to investigate dimensions related to employee reactions (refer to de Waal, 2003; Jawahar 2007; Kuvaas, 2007; Levy & Williams, 2004).

The literature suggests that interest on employee reactions is a result of growing concern on social context of performance management (Levy & Williams, 2004). Several previous research studies emphasise that performance management is about ownership, input, the perception of being valued and being part of the organisational team (Keeping & Levy, 2000; Levy & Williams, 2004). Therefore, performance management systems cannot be designed without considering and accommodating the human element (e.g., de Waal, 2003; Kuvaas, 2007; Levy & Williams, 2004). Kuvaas (2007) stated that performance management positively influences employees' outcomes only if they experience positive reactions. Therefore, employee reactions to performance management is identified as a measure of performance management effectiveness (Jawahar, 2007; Selvarajan & Cloninger, 2012; Shrivastava & Purang, 2011).

Employee reactions to performance management play a key role in the development of favourable attitudes towards job and work context (Jawahar 2007; Kavanagh, Benson, & Brown, 2007; Levy & Williams, 2004; Selvarajan & Cloninger, 2012; Shrivastava & Purang, 2011). Jawahar (2005) found that positive employee reactions enhance their motivation to increase job performance. Kavanagh et al. (2007) stated that employee reactions have potential to influence employees' acceptance of the performance management process. Selvarajan and Cloninger (2012) provided evidence that higher levels of perceived fairness and accuracy lead to higher levels of employee satisfaction with performance management by motivating employees to improve performance in the future. Employee participation in the feedback process had shown to decrease employee's satisfaction with performance

management, providing an impression of effectiveness (Shrivastava&Purang, 2011; Soltani et al., 2004).

Building on the literature previously presented (such as Boswell & Boudreau, 2000; Gravina&Siers, 2011; Selvarajan&Cloninger, 2012; Shrivastava&Purang, 2011) specific characteristics of performance management predict employees' reactions to performance management effectiveness, this is hypothesised in the following:

H1: Characteristics of performance management predicts employees' reactions to performance management effectiveness

Due to the lack of empirical studies on medium-sized enterprises that provides a specific list of characteristics of performance management in the literature, the characteristics of performance management were derived through the factor analysis (for all statistical procedures refer to Hair, Black, Babin, Anderson, & Tatham, 2006). In a similar vein, for the current article, the item measures for performance management effectiveness were derived through the exploratory factor analysis.

Medium-sized enterprises in Sri Lanka

This section uses the term SME, in general, to refer to the combined category of small and medium enterprises. Specific reference is made to medium-sized enterprises as and when information is available.

In terms of the number of establishments operating in the country, 91.8% of the establishments were micro enterprises, where as 7% were small, 1% were medium and the balance 0.2% were large enterprises. However, in terms of number of persons engaged, 44.5% of persons were engaged in micro enterprises, 17.6% were in small enterprises, 12.9% were in medium enterprises, and 24.9% were in large enterprises (Department of Census and Statistics, 2015). Further, the larger the size of the establishment, the greater the chance that

the establishment to be controlled by a male. Accordingly, 26.3%, 8.3%, 6.1% and 4.6% of the firms belonging to micro, small, medium and large enterprises, respectively, were controlled by females (Department of Census and Statistics, 2015). With regard to the legal status of the establishment, the sole ownership is the dominant legal status of 94% of micro and 66% of small enterprises. However, sole ownership is 20% in large enterprises and 37% in medium-sized enterprises. 50% of medium and 61% of large scale establishments were condensed in urban areas where as 74% of the micro establishments were in rural areas (Department of census and statistics, 2015).

When considering the management of SMEs, due to the lack of proper organization structure, job design and HR planning, SMEswerefaced with issues in the effective use of physical and human resources. First, SMEs are lagging behind in the adoption of systematic methods of recruitment and selection (Priyanath, 2010). Second, SMEs face difficulties in attracting employees due to their smaller size, from which especially small enterprises are mainly suffer from. Small and medium enterprises are sought people who could perform multi-tasks due to their smaller size. However, they face difficulties in attracting people. Even though people are hired, there capabilities need to be enhanced prior to the allocation of job tasks, and once their capabilities are enhanced to an acceptable level, they leave the workplace for better prospects.

Small and medium enterprises adhere to government stipulated minimum wages and conditions stipulated by wages boards, and Shop and Office Employees (Regulation of Employment and Remuneration) Act of 1954 and Factories Ordinance of 1942 for working hours and overtime. Employee relations at SMEs are governed by the available legislation such as Employment of Women, Young Persons and Children Act of 1956, Payment of Gratuity Act of 1983, Employees' Provident Fund Act of 1958, Employees' Trust Fund Act

of 1980, Workmen's Compensation Ordinance of 1934, and Maternity Benefits Ordinance of 1939 (Sarveswaran, 2000).

To enhance the management practices of SMEs, the Federation of Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Sri Lanka (FCCISL), introduced a scheme named Entrepreneur of the Year Award, which conducted for the 20th year in 2015 covering each size category of small, medium, large and extra-large enterprises at provincial and national level, and also with special recognition scheme for women entrepreneurs (FCCISL, 2014). This scheme evaluates people management aspects under several headings such as employees and provision of facilities, productivity and quality, and statutory responsibilities.

Overall, issues faced by SMEs hamper the growth of the Sri Lankan SME sector. The level of adoption and effectiveness of management practices ultimately influence SMEs' access to finance, and their competitiveness, market relevance and entrepreneurship. Yet, these issues are not limited to Sri Lankan SMEs.

Methodology

Sample

In the Sri Lankan context, the literature supports identifying enterprises with fewer than 10 employees as micro-enterprises, those with 10 to 49 employees as small; those with 50 to 99 employees as medium-sized; and those with more than 100 employees as large (Ponnamperuma, 2000; Sri Ranjith & Banda, 2014). The years of business operation is also a key factor in deciding how systematically enterprises operate their businesses in Sri Lanka (Wijetunge, 2014). Wijetunge (2014) found that SMEs with more than 7 years of business operation were actively engaged in business planning process in Sri Lanka. The Federation of Chamber of Commerce and industry of Sri Lanka (2014) classifies enterprises based on total investment, where it identifies enterprises with total investment less than 5 million Sri

Lankan Rupees (or 38,000/= US Dollars) as small, and between 5 to 50 million Sri Lankan Rupees (or 380,000/= US Dollars) as medium.

Based on the above discussion, three sample selection criteria were set for the study, i.e., total number of employees should be between 50 to 99; the years of business operation should be more than 7 years; total investment should be between 5 to 50 million Sri Lankan Rupees. These three sample selection criteria led to isolate medium-sized enterprises that have the potential to practice performance management. The Department of Census and Statistics of Sri Lanka provided a list of 65 medium-sized enterprises that fulfilled the selection criteria set for the study. It was decided to collect data covering the entire study population (population = sample) during the first quarter of 2014.

To ease the data collection, a contact person was identified from each enterprise. The contact persons together with the author of this paper selected a random sample covering a cross-section of employees from each enterprise to distribute the self-administered survey questionnaire. A multiple constituency approach had been adopted and collected data from employees (supervisor-level or above) and the person responsible in administering performance management from each enterprise. Six per cent of the enterprises had a dedicated HRM unit/department. Over 70 per cent of the enterprises had appreciable knowledge on the importance of quality improvement for survival and growth. Over 60 per cent of the enterprises had implemented some kind of quality initiative, such as Japanese 5S and quality audits with Sri Lanka Standards Institute to obtain quality accreditation.

Forty one responses were received from the person responsible in administering performance management in the 41 enterprises (response rate 63% [41/65]). They provided data on the nature of performance targets and most commonly used performance criteria for employees. Two hundred and seventy responses were received from employees. With regard to the demographics of the sample, 19 per cent represented front-line staff, 52 per

centrepresented first-level management, and 29 per cent represented middle-level management. 68 per cent of the respondents were male while 32 per cent of the respondents were female. All participants were in the age range of 23 to 48 years, where mean age was 31 years (SD = 4 years). Sixty four per cent had 13 years of schooling as the highest level of education, 26 per cent had diploma level qualification (post-secondary) related to their current job as the highest level of qualification, and 10 per cent had bachelor's degree as the highest level of qualification. With regard to years of experience in the present workplace, 45 per cent had three years of work experience, 37 per cent had three to five years of work experience, and 18 per cent had more than 10 years of work experience.

Measures

Due to the difficulty of finding readily available scale items, multiple-item measures were developed for the study base don the guidelines recommended by Nunnally (1978). In doing so, first, the domain of the relevant construct was specified. Second, items were developed to map the construct's conceptual definition. Finally, the items were pre-tested on a convenience sample that fit with the intended sample of the study and revised accordingly. A brief description of the measures is as follows. All item measures are given in Appendix 1.

The nature of performance targets. 11-item measure on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree) was developed. The person responsible in administering performance management responded.

Commonly used performance criteria. The respondents listed commonly used performance criteria across the organisation. The person responsible in administering performance management responded.

Characteristics of performance management. 28-item measure captured employees' perceptions towards performance management. The items were on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree).

Performance management effectiveness. 11-item measure captured employees' reactions towards performance management effectiveness. The items were on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree).

Methods of data analysis

Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) were performed on the item measures of performance management characteristics and performance management effectiveness, separately. We tested EFA using SPSS for appropriate (a) internal consistency reliability, (b) factor structure (c) convergent validity, (d) discriminant validity and (e) construct reliability (CR) to identify any issues with multicollinearity and response bias; convergent validity was measured by average variance extracted (AVE) and discriminant validity was measured by the square root of AVE (for all statistical procedures refer to Hair et al., 2006). The criteria adhered to are: eigenvalues of all components should not be less than 1.0; the loadings should be 0.50 or greater to be considered practically significant; Cronbach's alpha values of each factor extracted and overall measure should be greater than 0.7; AVE values should be above 0.5; square root of AVE for a given construct should be greater than the correlation between that construct and all other constructs. Wilks' Lambda statistic was obtained to check whether any differences exist among the firms. The results revealed that significant differences do not exist ($p > 0.05$) among the firms on our study variables (for all statistical procedures refer to Hair et al., 2006). To test common method

variance we used Harman's single-factor test; neither single factor emerged from this analysis nor was there a general factor that could account for the majority of variance fulfilling the recommended guidelines of Podsakoff et al. (2003). The results suggested that common method variance is not a concern in our data, and thus is unlikely to confound the interpretations of results. To examine the hypothesized relationships, structural equation modeling (SEM) with maximum likelihood estimation was performed using AMOS (for SEM procedures refer to Arbuckle, 2007).

Results

The first objective of the study was to identify the nature of performance targets and performance criteria used by medium-sized enterprises. With regard to the nature of performance targets, the 11-item measure on performance targets had Cronbach's alpha reliability of 0.802. The KMO statistic was above the customary reference point of 0.5 for a satisfactory factor analysis to proceed. Bartlett's test of sphericity is significant – associated probability was less than the customary reference point of 0.05 for a satisfactory factor analysis to proceed. Principal component factor analysis yielded a set of three factors, which explained 84 per cent (84.11) of the variance. Factor 1 was labelled as "individual", Factor 2 as "departmental", Factor 3 as "corporate". The items, factor loadings, and reliability statistics are shown in Table 1.

Take in Table 1

With regard to performance criteria used by medium-sized enterprises, the most commonly used performance criteria are shown in Table 2. As can be seen in Table 2, the level of

knowledge and skills pertinent for the job is used as a performance criterion by all the enterprises in the sample (100%).

Take in Table 2

The second objective of the study was to identify the characteristics of performance management in medium-sized enterprises. The 28-item measure on the characteristics of performance management had Cronbach's alpha reliability of 0.781. The KMO statistic was above the customary reference point of 0.5 for a satisfactory factor analysis to proceed. Bartlett's test of sphericity is significant – associated probability was less than the customary reference point of 0.05 for a satisfactory factor analysis to proceed. Principal component factor analysis yielded a set of six factors, which explained 75 per cent (74.57) of the variance. These six characteristics are identified as focus, target setting, administrative work procedures, interdependency, integration with other HRM functions, and responsibility. The items, factors, factor loadings, and reliability statistics are shown in Table 3. In terms of the factor loadings, the findings suggest that the factors of focus, target setting and administrative work procedures represent a large proportion of the total variance than the other three factors.

Take in Table 3

The third objective of the study was to identify characteristics of performance management that predict performance management effectiveness in medium-sized enterprises. To fulfil the third objective of the study, first, employees' reactions to performance management effectiveness was assessed. The 11-item measure on performance management effectiveness

had Cronbach's alpha reliability of 0.824. The KMO statistic was above the customary reference point of 0.5 for a satisfactory factor analysis to proceed. Bartlett's test of sphericity is significant – associated probability was less than the customary reference point of 0.05 for a satisfactory factor analysis to proceed. Principal component factor analysis yielded a set of three factors, which explained 58 per cent (57.59) of the variance. Factor 1 was labelled as “utility”, Factor 2 as “acceptable”, Factor 3 as “relevant”. The items, factors, factor loadings, and reliability statistics are shown in Table 4.

Take in Table 4

Means, standard deviations and zero-order correlations between the variables are shown in Table 5. The square root of average variance extracted (AVE) for each construct is also shown in Table 5. The values of the square root of AVE for a given construct were compared with the correlation between that construct and all other constructs. The analysis showed that the square root of AVE for a given construct is greater than the correlation between that construct and all other constructs, suggesting adequate discriminant validity.

Take in Table 5

Second, to identify the characteristics of performance management that predict performance management effectiveness in medium-sized enterprises, structural equation modelling was used. The structural model achieved a good level of fit having $\chi^2/df = 2.587$, GFI = 0.985, CFI = 0.990, and RMSEA=0.061. The summary of analysis is provided in Table 6. The results shown in Table 6 suggest that all the six characteristics of performance

management (namely focus, target setting, administrative work procedures, interdependency, integration with other HRM functions, and responsibility) significantly predict the three areas of effectiveness (utility, acceptable, and relevant). This supports H1. That is, with a standardized regression coefficient of .645 ($p < .001$), focus had the highest effect on utility. With a standardized regression coefficient of .364 ($p < .001$), interdependency had the highest effect on acceptability. With a standardized regression coefficient of .374 ($p < .001$), responsibility had the highest effect on relevancy. As can be seen in Table 6, the coefficient of determination of .657 suggests that six characteristics account for 66 per cent of the variation of utility. The coefficient of determination of .615 suggests that six characteristics account for 62 per cent of the variation of acceptability. The coefficient of determination of .583 suggests that six characteristics account for 58 per cent of the variation of relevance. Therefore, all six characteristics significantly positively predict all the three areas of performance management effectiveness. This supports the hypothesis of the study.

Take in Table 6

Discussion of results

Since previous research had not been selective regarding the size of SMEs investigated, evidence provided for the existence and practice of performance management is very pessimistic. In this context, the present study investigated performance management practices of medium-sized enterprises in Sri Lanka. To suit the purpose of the study, a sample of medium-sized enterprises were randomly selected that fulfilled the selection criteria set for the study. The intention of imposing these selection criteria was to identify the ways in which

performance management would be practiced by medium-sized enterprises if they had the opportunity, capacity and attitude to do so.

With regard to the first objective, the underlying dimensions of targets set for performance management were identified as linked to individual, departmental and corporate levels. As emphasised in the previous studies (such as de Waal, 2003; Kuvaas, 2007; Gravina&Siers, 2011), the findings also reveal that performance management should support the achievement of targets addressing the needs of organisational, departmental, and individual levels.

Performance criteria used in medium-sized enterprises were identified to represent technical, business, personal, and intellectual capabilities. These criteria were derived by summarising the lists of items provided by the person responsible in administering performance management from each enterprise. When creating subsets, theoretical support for grouping the criteria was taken from previous studies such as Morris, Davis, Allen, Avila, & Chapman (1991) and Pettijohn et al. (2001). The performance criteria of technical, business, personal, and intellectual capabilities, which were identified in the analysis, were used across job categories to evaluate job performance in Sri Lanka.

With regard to the second objective, the six characteristics were identified in the analysis as focus, target setting, administrative work procedures, interdependency, integration with other HRM functions, and responsibility. This finding supports the literature (such as Biron et al., 2011; Shrivastava&Purang, 2011) that states one of the key characteristics of performance management should be its integration with other HRM functions. Although some previous studies (such as Soltani et al., 2004) provide evidence for the lack of utilization of performance management information for diagnosing training and development needs, the findings of the present study provide evidence for such usage.

Three features of performance management effectiveness were identified as utility, acceptable and relevant. Previous research (such as Biron et al., 2011; Haines III & St-Onge, 2012; Shrivastava&Purang, 2011) also identified that employee perceptions towards performance management effectiveness involve aspects of fair, useful, and valid. With regard to the third objective, analysis revealed that performance management characteristics significantly positively predict performance management effectiveness as presented in the section on *Results*.

Conclusions and implications

Based on the results and discussion of the results presented above, medium-sized enterprises in Sri Lanka set performance management targets and these are linked to individual, departmental and corporate levels. Six performance management characteristics were identified as focus, target setting, administrative work procedures, interdependency, integration with other HRM functions, and responsibility. Three areas of performance management effectiveness were identified as utility, acceptable and relevant. It was revealed all the six characteristics significantly positively predict all the three areas of effectiveness supporting H1. Overall, the findings of the study have both theoretical and practical implications.

In terms of the contribution of the study for the existing body of literature, first, it is very rare to find previous studies that had investigated performance management in medium-sized enterprises for comparison. Hence, the current study addressed a gap that has not received due attention in the literature. Second, the findings suggest that medium-sized enterprises relate performance management to different organisational levels of corporate, departmental and individual; adopt a cyclical process with different stages, such as planning, review and reward. In other words, performance management in medium-sized

enterprises serve different purposes such as making between person decisions (such as promotion), making within person decisions (such as training needs), and making decisions on system maintenance (such as assessing the achievement of targets). Serving these diverse purposes support arguments of Cleveland, Murphy, and Williams (1989). When medium-sized enterprises are investigated under the common category of SMEs such adoptions may not become prominent.

Third, academics and practitioners need valid and reliable multidimensional measurement scales for the evaluation of performance management practices. The present study developed item measures that were empirically based and was shown to be valid and reliable in the context of Sri Lankan medium-sized enterprises. Fourth, the measures proposed in this study could be used to serve as a diagnostic tool to assess and analyse issues in connection to the usage of performance management systems in medium-sized enterprises and could take necessary corrective actions to improve them. Overall, the findings of the study have provided baseline data that would be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research in this area.

In terms of the contribution of the study for practice, medium-sized enterprises in the sample have devoted considerable energy in implementing performance management practices. This is a very positive signal for the practice of HRM since performance management is one of the key areas designed to manage, support and develop workforce in any organisation. Yet, the mean values shown in Table 5 suggest that considerable improvements are needed in the level of adoption. All the mean values were at moderate level (around 3 on a five point Likert scale). Employee reactions imply utilisation, relevance and acceptability are key areas of performance management effectiveness. Overall, the findings of the study provide some encouragement to HRM professionals that employees in medium-sized enterprises appreciate efforts taken in practicing performance management. However,

considerable improvements are needed in the level of adoption of performance management practices. Use of formal criteria for setting performance targets, aligning targets with corporate, team and individual objectives, implementing formal performance evaluation, and obtaining employee feedback of performance effectiveness could be considered as essential elements of the performance improvement in medium-sized enterprises.

With regard to the limitations of the study and areas for future research, the most frequently used criterion to distinguish SMEs is the number of employees. Yet, the present study imposed two more criteria in terms of years of business existence and total investment. As a result, the sample of the study may not represent the majority of medium-sized enterprises operating worldwide. Further, since Sri Lanka being a South Asian developing country, socio-cultural aspects could influence the conduct of performance management. Hence, more research in different country contexts may provide information for comparative purposes. Further, this research was designed as a cross-sectional study employing survey methodology. Therefore, future research could investigate specific areas of performance management such as top management involvement. Further, future studies could incorporate qualitative methodology to provide more depth for better understanding. Such investigations may also be able to unearth any dissatisfaction employees have with performance management. Furthermore, future research could investigate medium-sized enterprises that adopted various types of management such as virtual, family and cooperative, to name a few. In addition, it is possible to assume that any changes in the practices of medium-sized enterprises would be due to external pressures. Many of the enterprises in the sample are in the process of making their management processes more systematic by gradually moving towards quality accreditations. Therefore, it would be interesting for future studies to investigate the influence of external environment on the adoption of performance management.

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Tables

TABLE 1. FACTOR ANALYSIS – PERFORMANCE TARGETS

	F1: Individual	F2: Departmental	F3: Corporate
Encourages self-management of individual performance	.871		
Targets are tailored to match the job holder	.867		
Targets are realistic	.862		
Targets are achievable	.850		
Targets are very specific on what should be achieved	.724		
Organisation identifies the jobs that are critical to its success		.874	
Targets are set within the context of departmental plans		.862	
Targets are set within the context of departmental objectives		.773	
Targets are set within the context of corporate objectives			.897
The relationship between what job holders perform and financial results is clear			.834
Targets are set within the context of corporate mission			.741
Explained variation	43.30	22.55	18.26
Eigenvalue	3.46	1.80	1.46
Cronbach's alpha	.74	.71	.74
AVE	.73	.67	.68
Construct reliability	.95	.80	.87

Note: n = 41.

TABLE 2. COMMONLY USED PERFORMANCE CRITERIA

Performance Criteria	Assessed in performance management %
Technical related qualities:	
Level of knowledge and skill requirements pertinent to the job	100
Ability to meet the required standards of quality output	90
Ability to device work methods to meet deadlines	100
Business related qualities:	
Knowledge of the core business	85
Knowledge of how units/departments interact	70
Knowledge of external environment of the business	70
Knowledge of how organisation functions	85
Personal qualities:	
Interpersonal skills	90
Team working skills	90
Attitude to meet targets	90
Ability to perform job tasks with minimum supervision	100
Intellectual qualities:	
Ability to draw conclusions from data	60
Ability to search and review information	50
Ability to think logically	75
Ability of make decisions without undue delay	90
Oriented to achieve results	85
Ability to produce desired results	100
Initiative	95

Note: n = 41.

TABLE 3.CHARACTERISTICS OF PERFORMANCE MANAGEMENT

	F1: Focus	F2: Target setting	F3: Administrative work procedures	F4: Interdependency	F5: Integration with other HRM functions	F6: Responsibility
Performance management is a continuous process which improves my performance overtime	.808					
My targets are constantly updated in line with business requirements	.802					
Performance management has clear internal control focus	.790					
Performance management assesses my performance against jointly agreed targets.	.786					
Performance management provides insight into the relationship between business strategy and my targets	.716					
My work targets are fair enough to measure performance for the given period	.714					
Performance management process in my organisation is transparent		.805				
I am allowed to participate when my work targets are required to be changed		.782				
My immediate supervisor shows concerns over my feelings when my work targets are proposed to be changed		.781				
My immediate supervisor involves in setting/changing my targets		.752				
My targets are aligned with my immediate supervisor's responsibilities		.723				
My organisation demonstrates respected for employees when setting/changing targets		.710				
My work targets covers sufficient areas for fair evaluation by my immediate supervisor			.795			
Sufficient information on my performance is available with my immediate supervisor			.765			
Performance management is fairly administrated throughout the workplace			.717			
Performance management encourages to develop multi-skills				.833		
I have an understanding on how my work affects others in the workplace				.794		
When I fail to achieve my targets others' work performance will also be affected				.771		

Performance management encourages collaboration between units/departments							.703
Performance management encourages learning and sharing experiences							.796
Promotion decisions of my organisation are based on the results of performance management							.786
Training is provided by my organisation based on the results of performance management							.763
Financial decisions of my organisation are based on the results of performance management							.721
Any change to my job responsibilities are based on the results of performance management							.718
Performance management is useful in selecting and prioritizing my job tasks							.803
Because of performance management I know the tasks that I am responsible.							.771
Because of performance management my immediate supervisor can easily follow up my progress							.754
Performance feedback is useful for me to improve my work performance							.701
Explained variation	30.68	19.66	9.82	5.44	4.92	4.05	
Eigenvalue	9.20	2.89	2.05	1.63	1.48	1.22	
Cronbach's alpha	.795	.738	.705	.712	.776	.782	
AVE	.58	.57	.56	.64	.58	.60	
Construct reliability	.92	.92	.83	.84	.88	.81	

Note: n = 270.

TABLE 4. PERFORMANCE MANAGEMENT EFFECTIVENESS

	F1: Utility	F2: Acceptable	F3: Relevant
My targets help me to satisfy our stakeholders	.789		
Performance management in my organisation is useful	.787		
Performance management encourages me to work	.778		
Performance management is widely used in my organisation	.732		
I am satisfied with performance management in my organisation		.826	
The results of the performance management is fair		.810	
I can ask clarifications for performance decisions made on me		.777	
Performance management helps me to plan my future			.759
Performance management ultimately improves how my organisation performs			.839
Performance management is important to my job			.725
Performance management is important to my unit/department			.725
Explained variation	35.93	13.66	8.00
Eigenvalue	4.67	1.77	1.04
Cronbach's alpha	.83	.76	.70
AVE	.62	.63	.61
Construct reliability	.95	.87	.76

Note: n = 270.

TABLE 5. CORRELATIONS

	Mean	S.D.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1 Focus	3.07	.47	.76								
2 Target setting	3.15	.49	.305*	.75							
3 Administrative work procedures	3.28	.53	.310**	.456**	.74						
4 Interdependency	3.11	.55	.442**	.381**	.424**	.80					
5 Integration with other HRM functions	2.98	.51	.448**	.493**	.278**	.384**	.76				
6 Responsibility	3.02	.75	.280**	.467**	.419**	.384**	.104	.77			
7 Utility	3.21	.51	.659**	.688**	.525**	.558**	.535**	.317**	.78		
8 Acceptable	3.23	.58	.541**	.511**	.580**	.631**	.485**	.466**	.438**	.79	
9 Relevant	3.06	.77	.522**	.565**	.592**	.587**	.678**	.523**	.483**	.484**	.78

Note: * p < 0.05 and ** p < 0.01; diagonal entries, square root of AVE; off-diagonal entries, correlations between constructs; n = 270.

TABLE 6. SUMMARY OF RESULTS: STRUCTURAL MODEL COEFFICIENTS

Path	Standardized regression estimate and significance	Squared multiple correlation
Focus --->Utility	.645 ^{***}	.657
Target setting --->Utility	.207 ^{**}	
Administrative work procedures --->Utility	.194 ^{**}	
Interdependency --->Utility	.138 [*]	
Integration with other HRM functions --->Utility	.200 ^{**}	
Responsibility --->Utility	.116 [*]	
Focus --->Acceptable	.180 [*]	.615
Target setting --->Acceptable	.168 [*]	
Administrative work procedures --->Acceptable	.263 ^{***}	
Interdependency --->Acceptable	.364 ^{***}	
Integration with other HRM functions --->Acceptable	.287 ^{***}	
Responsibility --->Acceptable	.184 [*]	
Focus --->Relevant	.159 [*]	.583
Target setting --->Relevant	.211 ^{**}	
Administrative work procedures --->Relevant	.174 [*]	
Interdependency --->Relevant	.127 [*]	
Integration with other HRM functions --->Relevant	.179 [*]	
Responsibility --->Relevant	.374 ^{***}	

Note. ^{*} p<.05, ^{**} p<.01, ^{***} p<.001; n = 270.

Appendix 1

The nature of performance targets:

- Encourages self-management of individual performance
- Targets are tailored to match the job holder
- Targets are realistic
- Targets are achievable
- Targets are very specific on what should be achieved
- Organisation identifies the jobs that are critical to its success
- Targets are set within the context of departmental plans
- Targets are set within the context of departmental objectives
- Targets are set within the context of corporate objectives
- Targets are set within the context of corporate mission
- The relationship between what job holders perform and financial results is clear

Characteristics of performance management:

- Performance management is a continuous process which improves my performance overtime
- My targets are constantly updated in line with business requirements
- Performance management has clear internal control focus
- Performance management assesses my performance against jointly agreed targets.
- Performance management provides insight into the relationship between business strategy and my targets
- My work targets are fair enough to measure performance for the given period

Performance management process in my organisation is transparent
I am allowed to participate when my work targets are required to be changed
My immediate supervisor shows concerns over my feelings when my work targets are proposed to be changed
My immediate supervisor involves in setting/changing my targets
My targets are aligned with my immediate supervisor's responsibilities
My organisation demonstrates respected for employees when setting/changing targets
My work targets cover sufficient areas for fair evaluation by my immediate supervisor
Sufficient information on my performance is available with my immediate supervisor
Performance management is fairly administrated throughout the workplace
Performance management encourages collaboration between units/departments
Performance management encourages to develop multi-skills
I have an understanding on how my work affects others in the workplace
When I fail to achieve my targets others' work performance will also be affected
Performance management encourages learning and sharing experiences
Promotion decisions of my organisation are based on the results of performance management
Training is provided by my organisation based on the results of performance management
Financial decisions of my organisation are based on the results of performance management
Any change to my job responsibilities are based on the results of performance management
Performance management is useful in selecting and prioritizing my job tasks
Because of performance management I know the tasks that I am responsible.
Because of performance management my immediate supervisor can easily follow up my progress
Performance feedback is useful for me to improve my work performance

Performance management effectiveness:

My targets help me to satisfy our stakeholders
Performance management in my organisation is useful
Performance management encourages me to work
Performance management is widely used in my organisation
I am satisfied with performance management in my organisation
The results of the performance management is fair
I can ask clarifications for performance decisions made on me
Performance management helps me to plan my future
Performance management ultimately improves how my organisation performs
Performance management is important to my job
Performance management is important to my unit/department